

Development of the Agouti platform for the European Observatory of Wildlife

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Abstract

Wild mammal monitoring carried out by ENETWILD with camera traps leans heavily on Agouti (<https://agouti.eu>), a platform that simplifies wildlife monitoring by offering a complete solution for managing, processing and storing images and data from camera-traps projects. ENETWILD uses Agouti for the estimation of abundance of wildlife population using camera traps, such as wild boar across Europe. ENETWILD facilitates platform improvements to better support this goal, in particular the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), which in 2024 consisted in 70 sites spread across all of Europe. A main goal on the EOW is to collect independent information on wildlife population abundance and trends over time. Agouti plays a central role in the process, and several major development sprints have been completed to better support the EOW, ENETWILD, and the camera trapping community in general. The present report describes the development work completed as part of the ENETWILD project 2.0.

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Key words: mammals, monitoring, camera trapping, density estimation, wild boar

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1 Introduction

The Agouti platform¹ for camera trapping simplifies wildlife monitoring by offering a complete solution for managing, processing and storing camera trap data (Casaer et al. 2019). The ENETWILD project uses Agouti for the estimation of abundance of wildlife population using camera traps, such as wild boar, across Europe, and facilitates platform improvements towards to this goal (ENETWILD consortium et al. 2022, 2023a, 2023c). These activities are coordinated by the ENETWILD sub-project European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW; ENETWILD consortium et al. 2023b, 2024), which in 2024 consisted 70+ sites spread across all of Europe.

A main goal on the EOW is to collect “Independent information on wildlife population abundance and trends over time”. Agouti plays a central role in the process, and several major development sprints have been completed to better support the EOW participants, ENETWILD and the camera trapping community in general.

This brief technical report describes the development work completed in the 2024 development cycle of Agouti as defined in the ENETWILD Specific Contract 2, Work Package 3.1.

1.1 Background and terms of reference

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to the ENETWILD2 Consortium to improve the Agouti application so to further facilitate and improve the processing of camera trap data of wildlife populations.

Contractor/Beneficiary: University of Torino, Italy

Contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01 Specific Contract SC02

2 Activities and deliverables

2.1 Improvement of the Agouti AI

Efficiently processing the hundreds of thousands of camera-trap images collected by EOW participants requires sufficiently accurate artificial intelligence (AI). Agouti has offered several iterations of a species classification model for Europe. Each iteration of the model was trained with an expanded dataset, which increased overall accuracy and spatial coverage. As of March 2025 version 5 of the European species model is available to Agouti users and Version 6 is scheduled for release by April 2025.

2.1.1 The European species model

While version 5 of the European species model was a major release that included lots of annotated image-level data collected by the EOW participants, overall performance of the model seems to have levelled off at 92% correct at the image level, for 339 taxa. There is a clear spread across taxa. We find poor performance for some species, notably *Capra hircus*

¹ www.agouti.eu
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(71.4%), *Lutra lutra* (73.2%) and *Martes foina* (81.7%), and high performance for others, for example *Lepus Europaeus* (99.4%), *Meles meles* (97.3%) and *Erinaceus europaeus* (96.8%). Indicating a specific cause for this variation in performance is difficult because there is lots of variation in image quality, sequence length, camera placement and camera types that may influence the performance of models.

What has become clear is that just adding more image-level data will not necessary improve the model's accuracy. At the level of individual species, there seems to be a trade-off between the accuracy and precision of the model. Taking a highly specific set of images to train a species may lead to a high precision but poor accuracy. In practical terms: the model will perform *well* on *Sus scrofa* from the same area that provided the training data, but poor on *Sus scrofa* captured in another area. Given the significant plasticity of many species across Europe, improving the overall accuracy of the model was a focus for version 6.

A second point of interest is the sequence-level performance of the AI. Camera traps are often set to take multiple images in a burst upon sensing motion. While this increases the chance of capturing at least one clear picture of the animal, it introduces another factor that complicates AI classification. After all, how to decide which image to use, or how to combine the individual images into one sequence-level classification? Especially when there is more than one animal in the frame this becomes challenging. Improving sequence-level performance of the European AI model was another focus for version 6.

The following development sprints were completed as part of the objectives mention above:

- (1) We improved the re-learning flow for existing models to incorporate AI-observations corrected by users. A job now runs daily to check for any observation that were added by the AI but have been corrected by the user. These cases are automatically added to the AI library so the model can learn from these mistakes and gradually improve over time.
- (2) We improved and expanded the validation dataset for AI model training, using EOW data amongst others. While this process is ongoing, the Agouti team has validated dozens of species and tens of thousands of bounding boxes. This cleaned and expanded validation dataset allow us to more effectively evaluate whether a newly trained model performs better, or worse, than the previous one.
- (3) We improved data loading to get external legacy datasets and more EOW data from Agouti into the training library. EOW data is now imported daily (see point 1) and a dozen legacy projects containing species data from Europe have been imported into Agouti.
- (4) We experimented with different workflows for classification. These experiments included, for example, excluding animal-shaped static objects such as posts or tree stumps from being incorrectly classified as animals. Also, we experimented with hierarchical models that utilize a multi-step classification process, where models first classify broadly and become more specific with each step. For example, first checking if a frame is empty, then a family-level classification (example: *Cervidae*),

species-level (*Cervus elaphus*) and optionally classification of age class, sex, behaviour or even individual identification of the animal. These experiments have yielded a template for such hierarchical models. More work is needed for development and to evaluate the performance compared to a more traditional one-step approach.

- (5) We identified which species performed poorly in the current models and addressed those directly. We selectively added more data for underrepresented or rare species that are important to the European model. Examples include: *Ursus arctos*, *Lynx pardinus/lynx*, *Alces alces*, *Capra pyrenaica/ibex* and many bird species.
- (6) We improved total counts on AI-sequence level as to better consolidate image-level predictions to sequence-level predictions. This yielded several new methods for tracking and counting bounding boxes across sequences of images. Performance depended highly on the number of animals present. With few individuals (<4) present performance was better compared to the old approach of taking the maximum number of bounding boxes in any image in the sequence. However, when larger groups of individuals were present or if sequences were very long, performance decreased. Furthermore, performance is species dependent. Further integration is needed, especially in combination with the hierarchical models described in point 4.
- (7) We upgraded the neural network architecture to RT-DETR and evaluated its performance. While not expected to completely replace the current architecture, RT-DETR seems promising as a quick first-step classification model that can quickly distinguish between animal, blank, human or vehicle classes. We are still exploring the application of this architecture to improve pre-screening of images on the presence of humans, so these can be filtered.

2.1.2 AI integration within Agouti

We improved the functioning, speed and stability of the AI for species recognition and counting. Amongst others, we fixed the AI queue indicator, we fixed the problem that deployments would sometimes remain hanging on “scheduled” or “processing” states, and we fixed cases where AI was running but did not in fact produce observations. These problems were caused by performance bottlenecks in the Agouti back-end in combination with a growing number of images being submitted to the AI.

To further scale the AI stability and performance, more work is needed to keep up with future growth. We Also added an option to run new AI models on top of already analysed deployments, and the option to rerun AI to update or replace classifications. And we added the possibility to selectively bulk-delete AI observations, for example in a specific deployment or specific species.

2.2 The Agouti user interface

2.2.1 Calibration and tracking

The deployment-calibration and animal-tracking tools are core features of Agouti that allow EOW users to easily collect the parameters needed to calculate population density estimates of wild boar and other wildlife (ENETWILD consortium et al. 2023c). The initial implementation was realized under ENETWILD. Based on experiences and feedback of users during the 2022 and 2023 EOW campaigns, we evaluated and improved the user interface.

Before the parameters needed to estimate animal densities can be calculated automatically, Agouti requires three inputs, namely: a valid camera calibration, a deployment calibration and digitized tracks of an animal moving through the camera view. One concern of users in the initial implementation was that there was no feedback about the presence or quality of the required inputs. Using the feedback, we improved the tools in three ways.

A first request was to add an indicator that allows users to see whether the required camera calibration was present in the system (Fig. 1) These parameters are stored centrally in Agouti for each unique combination of camera manufacturer, model and image resolution setting. This means that multiple calibrations may be required for the same camera model. The visual feedback to the user contains instructions on what to do when a camera calibration is missing. Agouti currently has camera calibrations available for 120+ camera/resolution combinations which covers most commonly used camera models. At this point, most users need not worry about camera calibrations and can start with digitizing their own deployments directly.

Figure 1: The calibration view now has an indicator warning the user in case the camera model calibration is missing.

The second request was to improve the deployment calibration interface. Deployment calibration is a required step that allows the system to reconstruct the ground surface in the view of a camera by digitizing two points of a calibration pole that is photographed at >15 different positions across the view. In Agouti, this is done by clicking on the image of the calibration pole and entering the height of these point on the stick (Fig. 2). We improved the deployment calibration interface by adding a button that generates two plots that can be used to visually assess the quality of the calibration (Fig. 2, right side). It was not yet possible to show a simple indicator based on some quantitative criterium, but this will be considered as soon as such an indicator becomes available. We have also improved the back-end mechanism of the calibration tools, which means faster and more reliable entry of points.

Figure 2: The deployment calibration view. A calibration point is added by clicking two points on the calibration pole, and entering the corresponding height. The plots at the right allow users to visually assess the deployment calibration quality, verifying that there was an even distribution of poles throughout the view, and that poles were reasonably upright.

The third feature that EOW users asked for was an improved animal-tracking interface. We have implemented both performance optimizations to the back-end and the option to interactively calculate the speed, distance, radius and angle of the tracked animal in real time (Fig. 3). This allows users to check whether the output data makes sense without having to export their whole project as a camtrap DP package (Bubickny et al. 2024) and inspecting those files. This streamlines the animal tracking process and reduces the tedious process of going back and forth between data export and data entry.

Figure 3: When tracking an animal, Agouti can now calculate the speed, distance to camera, radius and angle interactively. This allows users to spot errors during the digitization process.

2.2.1 Further improvements

We optimized the Agouti backend performance by addressing several bottlenecks, with a focus on the user experience. Both database and API performance was improved by rewriting slow queries and making adjustments to the data model. These changes are not directly visible to the user, but led to improvements because less resources are needed on the user's computer to work with Agouti. More work is needed to keep backend response times acceptable in the future, especially with the number of users and use if AI tools increasing.

As part of regular maintenance, we updated web and API components to keep Agouti secure. This included general patching against vulnerabilities as well as migrating to major new versions of underlying frameworks, which typically improve efficiency and stability as well.

We implemented load-dependent scaling of the IT infrastructure by moving to a managed cluster. This allowed for cost efficient scaling by using fewer server resources on low-traffic times, minimizing costs, while quickly increasing resources automatically at busy times, to maintain consistent performance. Another benefit of the cluster is that all components are scanned for vulnerabilities periodically and the process of deploying new versions of Agouti is automated. Finally, system monitoring ensures all components of Agouti are available and automatically restarted if they show problems. This greatly reduces the need to manually monitor servers and ensures optimal availability of Agouti to users.

Finally, we realised other minor new functionality requested by EOW users. This included updates to the user interface translations in seven languages, minor layout improvements, the addition of sequence information in camtrap DP packages and a tool to download images of a sequence directly from the annotation interface.

2.3 Agouti user support

The Agouti team runs an online helpdesk to provide users with support via email. This involved help with setting up projects, technical and data quality issues as well as general inquiries. This includes approximately 20 new EOW projects for the 2024 sampling season. Generally, users appreciate the personal contact with the Agouti helpdesk which highlights the importance of providing this to our users.

3 Assessment and results

All the actions mentioned in SC02 were completed.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the ENETWILD investments in the Agouti platform have significantly improved the stability and performance of the system and have made it easier for EOW participants to process the images collected across Europe.

5 Recommendations

Several further improvements of the Agouti platform are possible to better meet the EOW goals and facilitate users. These include (1) further improvement of the AI models, including hierarchical classification in which models are stacked; (2) improving the user guide with more detailed help texts to better guide users. This should include help in choosing an appropriate AI model; (3) automation of the tracking of animal paths in the camera-trap view, which is in theory possible by a combination of key point analysis (Shreyas & Sheth 2021) to recognize the body structure of animals and object tracking focusing on the estimated positions of the front feet. Major challenge include animals that do not move perpendicular through the view, distant animals that are too poorly visible due to obstructions of at night and cannot be assigned sufficient key points, and obstruction of animal feet by vegetation, implying that the model must calculate the most likely position for other key points, for example through a technique called skeletonization (Zago et al. 2020). These are cutting-edge computer-vision problems; (4) automation of the deployment calibration process. This can be done by using a calibration stick that has unique markings at several heights so it can be automatically recognized by the Agouti AI. By automating the deployment calibration process, a step that is now perceived as cumbersome by many users can be streamlined; Finally (5) we believe that it is desirable to develop tools and procedures for making camera-trap data in Agouti more FAIR, and to facilitate and guide users in sharing at least the metadata of their surveys, so that colleagues can take notice of the studies.

References

- Bubnicki, J. W., Norton, B., Baskauf, S. J., Bruce, T., Cagnacci, F., Casaer, J., ... & Desmet, P., 2024. Camtrap DP: an open standard for the FAIR exchange and archiving of camera trap data. *Remote Sensing in Ecology and Conservation*, 10, 283-295.
- Casaer, J., Milotic, T., Liefing, Y., Desmet, P., & Jansen, P.A., 2019. Agouti: A platform for processing and archiving of camera trap images. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 3, e46690.
- ENETWILD consortium, Liefing, Y., Casaer, J., Desmet, P., Rowcliffe, J. M., & Jansen, P.A., 2022. Update on the development of the Agouti platform for collaborative science with camera traps and a tool for wildlife abundance estimation. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 19, 7327E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Casaer, J., Jansen, P.A., Roy, D., Stephens, P. A., Blanco-Aguiar, J.A., ... & Smith, G.C., 2023a. Improvement of information technology tools to collect, process and analyse data on wildlife population. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 20, 8217E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Guerrasio, T., Pelayo Acevedo, P., Apollonio, M., Arnon, A., Barroqueiro, C., ... & Vicente, J., 2023b. Wild ungulate density data generated by camera trapping in 37 European areas: first output of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW). *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 20, 7892E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Guerrasio, T., Pelayo Acevedo, P., Apollonio, M., Arnon, A., Barroqueiro, C., ... & Vicente, J., 2023. Wild ungulate density data generated by camera trapping in 37 European areas: first output of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW). *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 20, 7892E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Guerrasio, T., Carniato, D., Acevedo, P., Apollonio, M., Arakelyan, M., ... & Scandura, M., 2024. Generating wildlife density data across Europe in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW). *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 21, 9084E.
- Shreyas, E., & Sheth, M. H., 2021. 3D object detection and tracking methods using deep learning for computer vision applications. pp. 735-738 in *2021 International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT)*. IEEE.
- Zago, M., Luzzago, M., Marangoni, T., De Cecco, M., Tarabini, M., & Galli, M., 2020. 3D tracking of human motion using visual skeletonization and stereoscopic vision. *Frontiers in bioengineering and biotechnology*, 8, 181.